

Appraisal Analysis of Attitude Resources in Russian “Belt and Road Initiative” News

Wu Ruixue, Prof. Xueai Zhao · Published 2018 · Political Science

As an obligatory stop of “the Belt and Road Initiative”, Russian true attitude on the implementation of this strategy is of great significance. Based on appraisal theory, this paper makes a qualitative and quantitative research of the composition of attitude resources of 15 news reports in ITAR-TASS which are randomly selected from January to June of 2017, aiming to explore the image that Russian mainstream media built of “the Belt and Road Initiative” and the ideology behind it. This paper... [Expand](#)

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Table 1. Distribution of Positive and Negative Attitude Resources

	Positive Attitude Resources	Negative Attitude Resources
Amount (N)	104	23
Percentage (%)	81.9%	18.1%

Table 1

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